

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

THE USE OF AUDIOVISUAL CONTENT (FILMS, SONGS, DIALOGUES AND PODCASTS) FOR THE SOCIO-CULTURAL DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE EDUCATION

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Abstract

The article explores the role of sociocultural competence in the process of foreign language learning. Special attention is given to the importance of cultural context in communication and the necessity of understanding cultural codes, traditions, and behavioral norms. The study emphasizes the value of audiovisual materials—films, songs, and podcasts—as effective tools for developing sociocultural awareness, authentic language acquisition, and intercultural sensitivity.

Keywords: sociocultural competence, language learning, audiovisual materials, cultural context, intercultural communication, authentic media.

Introduction

Modern education is faced with the need to integrate new technologies and teaching methods, which is especially important in the context of foreign language education.

In the “Conception of modernization of Kazakhstani education” states in order to achieve a goal oriented on a new conceptual basis in the study of foreign language, the communicative sphere becomes the substantive basis of the level model of foreign language education, within which the speech subject matter and the composition of typical situations are determined, ensuring the achievement of a socially sufficient level of foreign language education and the transition to professionally oriented foreign language education. In addition to innovative conceptual approaches to determining the purpose and subject content of foreign language education, the issue of using educational technologies should also be addressed from a new methodological perspective [1].

The use of digital and audio content such as films, songs, dialogues and podcasts opens up new horizons for the socio-cultural development of students. The problem is that traditional teaching methods are often unable to fully meet the needs of students in the context of globalization and cultural exchange.

The purpose of this work is to study the impact of digital content on language skills and cultural awareness of students, as well as to identify effective strategies for its application in the educational process. Important figures in this field are teachers who must adapt their methods to modern requirements, as well as content developers who create materials that meet educational standards.

The relevance of the topic is due to the growing role of digital technologies in education both in Kazakhstan and in the world. In the context of globalization and cultural diversity, it is important not only to teach the language, but also to develop socio-cultural

competencies, which is impossible without the use of modern audiovisual resources.

Within the framework of this topic, tasks can be considered, such as analyzing the effectiveness of various content formats, developing methodological recommendations for their integration into the educational process, and assessing the impact on student motivation.

Developing listening skills through podcasts and dialogues

Technology integration in foreign language instruction is recommended and successful in teaching all forms of speech activities, including professional-oriented speaking, writing, reading, and listening. Teaching professionally oriented speaking and listening requires the use of sound accompaniment and the development of situations that encourage students' oral utterances [2, p 79]. This can be achieved by emphasizing illustrative material. Podcasts and dialogues become increasingly beneficial tools that put students in the cultural context of native speakers while also fostering listening comprehension.

Students can be introduced to the customs, communication norms, holidays and etiquette of different nations using audio information, particularly in the form of brief podcasts and dialogues. The age characteristics of the students should be considered when selecting the content: texts should be clear, emotionally charged, along with visuals and definitions of new terms.

Children who regularly work with these resources gain a foundational understanding of foreign speech, learn intonation characteristics, and acquire adept at guessing word meanings from context.

Socio-cultural development through audiovisual materials

It takes more than just knowing grammar and vocabulary to communicate with representatives of a foreign-speaking country; knowing the context—is crucial

to achieving the highest level of language proficiency. In one culture, anything that is considered normal could be viewed as disrespectful or inappropriate in another. Even with flawless grammar, mistakes are easy to make if you are unaware of cultural standards. Building trustworthy connections, avoiding misunderstandings, and understanding cultural differences are all made possible by sociocultural competence. Many researchers, including R.P. Milrud and P.V. Sysoev, socio-cultural competence is understood as the capacity to compare and understand different linguo-cultural communities, interpret cultural distinctions, and respond appropriately in situations where intercultural understanding may be disrupted [3-4].

According to S.S. Kunanbayeva social and sociocultural sub competence, which forms a "secondary cognitive consciousness" in a linguistic personality as a concept and image of the world of another linguistic society, as well as forming "secondary constructions - knowledge" in its cognitive system, correlating with knowledge about the world and the language of a "foreign language". This type of sub competence is formed as "new" on the basis of "given" - secondary cognitive consciousness on the basis of its culture and language [4, p 110].

Authentic films show a "live" language, not an adaptation, but exactly as it is recognized in the nation where it is studied. Therefore, it is vital to use authentic materials to imitate real communication in order to fully depict the picture of the foreign-speaking world. When a teacher chooses the appropriate resources, students can explore the language and sociocultural context more thoroughly, and it becomes both required and feasible to replicate different scenarios.

Features of audiovisual material in foreign language teaching for the development of socio-cultural competence.

1. Live language in a real context

Slang, tone, gestures, and facial expressions are all examples of how people actually communicate in movies and television shows.

2. Cultural characteristics and daily life

Audiovisual materials reflect traditions, lifestyle, values, humor, and relationships between people. For example, you can learn from the film how an ordinary day goes, what holidays are celebrated, and how they behave in different situations.

3. Understanding non-verbal communication

Gestures, facial expressions, and distance in communication are all part of culture. Visual perception helps to better understand the context of communication and capture hidden meanings.

4. Forming an emotional connection with language

Songs, dialogues from films and real speech evoke emotions, make the learning process more interesting and motivating. This contributes to a deeper assimilation of the material.

5. Broadening horizons and eliminating stereotypes

Through art and media, a person can see the diversity within one culture, understand that it is not homogeneous, and learn to look at the world more broadly.

Conclusion

The development of sociocultural competence is an integral part of successful foreign language acquisition. Audiovisual materials play an important role in the formation of this competence. They allow you to immerse yourself in a living language environment, to perceive language not as a set of rules, but as a lively, dynamic and emotionally colored communication tool. Through them, students get the opportunity to "live" the culture, to experience it from the inside.

Thus, the inclusion of films, songs and other audiovisual sources in the educational process not only increases motivation and interest in learning, but also forms important intercultural communication skills that are necessary for modern people in a globalized world.

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